

Studies on the Behaviour of Cobalt and Calcium Soaps. Part IV : Solubilization of Water and Its Effect on Conductance Behaviour in Alcohols

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Solubilization of water in 1-butanol and 3-methyl-1-butanol has been studied in presence of cobalt and calcium soaps at 35-50°. Maximum additive concentration increases with increasing temperature and also with soap concentration below CMC. Addition of water increases the CMC of these soaps in alcohols. The conductance behaviour of soap solutions in presence of varying amounts of water is expressed by an equation $\log \lambda = A + B \log C$. Constants, $-A$ and $-B$ decrease with increasing amount of water. These values in 3-methyl-1-butanol are higher than the values in 1-butanol. Dissociation constant, K and molecular conductivity at infinite dilution, λ_{∞} have been calculated and are found to increase with increasing amount of water.

SOLUBILIZATION of water by non-aqueous solutions of surfactants is of considerable industrial importance in dry cleaning, engine lubrication and many other fields. In non-aqueous solvent systems the dissolved surfactants form micelles which are the seat of solubilizing action. A large number of systems in which water is solubilized have been studied by Palit and Coworkers¹⁻⁴. In many cases they found that amount of water solubilized is far greater than the amount of the solubilizer present. This is true where the soap is solubilizer and the temperature is raised beyond critical point which corresponds to a micellar change of state⁵. The solubilization of fatty alcohols in water⁶ is due to the micelle formation. Transition metal soaps solubilize⁷ oil insoluble dyes, higher acids, certain alkali soaps, water etc. The effect of 1-propanol, 2-propanol and propionic acid on the conductivity of aqueous soap solution has been studied⁸ and it has been suggested that these additives lower the CMC when added in small amounts. Bose and Coworkers⁹⁻¹¹ have studied the conductance of sodium soap solution in presence of varying amount of different alcohols. Recently the effect of water and aniline on the conductance behaviour of iron and cobalt soaps has been investigated¹² and it is found that cobalt caprylate is better solubilizer for water than iron caprylate.

In the present paper the ability of cobalt and calcium soaps solutions in 1-butanol and 3-methyl-1-butanol to solubilize water and the effect of this additive on conductance behaviour of the soaps in these solvents have been studied.

Experimental

The chemicals were purified and the soaps were prepared by the methods described earlier¹³. In

each case freshly prepared conductivity water (alkaline potassium permanganate) was used. The solubilization of water was studied by adding water to the soap solution dropwise from microburette with continuous shaking. The first excess over the solubilizing point gave the solution a turbid appearance which was noted. These results were confirmed by measuring the conductivity of the soap solution under similar conditions. All the measurements were made at constant temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) in a thermostat.

Results and Discussion

Solubilization of water: Solubilities of water (Table 1) in soap solutions are higher than in pure

TABLE 1—MAXIMUM ADDITIVE CONCENTRATION (MAC) OF WATER IN PRESENCE OF COBALT SOAPS IN 3-METHYL-1-BUTANOL AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (35-50°)

Temperature in °C	MAC (moles litre ⁻¹)							
	.000	.002	.003	.004	.005	.006	.008	.010M
	<i>Laurate</i>							
35	4.91	4.65	4.70	4.75	4.76	4.77	4.61	4.60
40	4.55	4.74	4.74	4.92	4.91	4.87	4.83	4.80
45	4.64	4.85	4.88	4.96	4.98	5.00	5.02	5.05
50	4.90	4.94	4.99	5.08	5.13	5.15	5.13	5.22
	<i>Oleate</i>							
35	4.21	4.33	4.33	4.40	4.42	4.41	4.40	4.39
40	4.55	4.69	4.69	4.76	4.81	4.78	4.74	4.78
45	4.64	4.84	4.84	4.89	4.95	4.96	4.95	4.93
50	4.90	4.93	4.97	5.06	5.13	5.12	5.10	5.22

alcohols which shows that water is solubilized in presence of these soaps. Solubilization is generally regarded as an effect which begins at CMC and does not increase greatly above a certain plateau

concentration^{14,15}. When the maximum additive concentration (MAC) is plotted against soap concentration it is found that MAC increases initially below CMC then it does not vary much with soap concentration and finally increases at higher concentration (Fig. 1a). These plots (Fig. 1b) for cobalt soaps show a continuous decrease above CMC in 1-butanol. It is found that the solubilizing power of cobalt laurate is more than oleate in 3-methyl-1-butanol.

Fig. 1 (a). Plots of maximum additive concentration (MAC) of water in calcium oleate solutions in 1-butanol at different temperatures (35-50°).

The plots of log MAC vs log C show an intersection of two straight lines at CMC. It is observed that the slopes below CMC are much higher than above this concentration and slopes of the calcium oleate in 1-butanol are independent of temperature. These values of cobalt oleate in both the alcohols and cobalt laurate in 1-butanol above CMC are independent of temperature. In other cases slopes vary with temperature in both the solvents.

Effect on conductance behaviour of soaps : Specific conductance, k of soap solution increases with increasing amount of water. Plots of specific conductance, k vs soap concentration, C in presence of varying amounts of water are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at the concentrations indicating CMC which is found to increase with increasing amount of water. It may be pointed out that CMC of soap solutions have been determined earlier¹⁶ from conductivity data in alcohols. Plots of CMC vs amount of water added show a linear variation of CMC for cobalt laurate whereas a change at 4.56 M concentration of water in other soaps in 1-butanol and 1.61 and 2.12 M water in cobalt laurate and cobalt oleate respectively in 3-methyl-1-butanol.

The plots of $\log \lambda$ vs $\log C$ are linear which show that in presence of varying amounts of water

the following relationship holds good :

$$\log \lambda = A + B \log C \quad \dots (i)$$

where A and B are constants.

The values of $-A$, $-B$ decrease with increasing amount of water. These constants for the soaps in 3-methyl-1-butanol are higher than the values in 1-butanol. A comparison of constant, $-A$ of soap in alcohols show the following order :

Calcium oleate > Cobalt laurate > Cobalt oleate.

Dissociation constant, K and molecular conductance at infinite dilution, λ_∞ can be calculated in presence of varying amounts of water by following relationship^{17,18}.

$$C^2 \lambda^2 = \frac{K \lambda_\infty^2}{4\lambda} - \frac{K \lambda_\infty^2}{4} \quad \dots (ii)$$

The plots of $C^2 \lambda^2$ vs $1/\lambda$ for soap solutions in alcohols are linear below CMC. The values of K and λ_∞ have been calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the linear plots. Soaps are much weaker electrolytes in alcohols due to lower dielectric constants. When water is solubilized in soap solutions the dielectric constant increases with increasing

Fig. 1(b) Plots of maximum additive concentration (MAC) of water in cobalt laurate solutions in 1-butanol at different temperatures (35-50°).

amount of water. It is observed that K increases with increase in water content in the solution. On comparison with the dissociation constants of soaps, it varies in the following order :

Cobalt oleate > Calcium oleate > Cobalt laurate

Molecular conductance at infinite dilution also increases with increasing amount of water. It is due to the overall decrease in the viscosity when water is added into it although some increase in viscosity occurs when concentration of soap increases in the system. λ_{∞} of soaps at different addition of water in solutions exhibit the following order :

Cobalt laurate > Calcium oleate > Cobalt oleate

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